

Studies in Heterocyclic Compounds—Part XXVII Synthesis and *in vitro* Antimicrobial Study of Some New 1,3-diaryl-5-(arylo) dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H, 5H)-Pyrimidinediones

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Four 2-thioxo pyrimidinediones, 1-phenyl-3-(*p*-methylphenyl)-, 1-phenyl-3-(*p*-bromophenyl)-, 1,3-bis(*p*-bromophenyl)- and 1-(*p*-bromophenyl)-3-(*p*-methylphenyl) dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinediones are synthesised and coupled with thirteen different diazotised bases to give the corresponding 5-(arylo) derivatives. The title compounds are subjected to *in vitro* screening against three micro-organisms, *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *P. pyocyanea* and many of these are found active.

THE short acting 2,4,6 (1H, 3H, 5H)-pyrimidinetri-ones and especially their sulphur analogues have been reported as therapeutic agents¹. 5,5-Diethylbarbituric acid commonly known as Veronal or Barbital has been widely used to induce sleep and to some extent as a sedative and an anaesthetic. The two derivatives were found to be more active hypnotics as compared to their oxygen analogues. Disubstituted dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinediones when injected intravenously into the animals, were found to show powerful hypnotic properties². 5-Alkyl derivatives of dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinediones also exhibited considerable promise as intravenous narcotics and as potent anaesthetic³⁻⁴.

1,3-Diphenyl-5-substituted dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinediones showed considerable anti-inflammatory activity and less toxicity⁵. Dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinediones having the methyl group in both the phenyl rings were found useful for the prevention and therapy of diseases caused by virus⁶.

These diones which contain an active methylene group could be condensed with aldehydes to give products which have been reported to be valuable pigments^{7,8}. 5-Aminocarbonyl dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinediones on screening were found to be useful as insecticides, acaricides, nematocides, molluscicides and agricultural fungicides⁹. Azo derivatives of thioxodiones have been reported to exhibit anticonvulsant properties which were absent in the corresponding thioxodiones¹⁰. Keeping the importance of dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinediones in therapy as well as in textile industry¹¹ in view and encouraged by the findings in respect of earlier work¹² on similar replacement of the active hydrogens of the β -diketones and β -keto esters, it was thought to extend this work by substitu-

ting the active hydrogen of the different 1,3-diaryl-dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinediones(I) by arylo groups.

The present paper describes the synthesis and *in vitro* screening of 1,3-diaryl-5-(arylo) dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinediones of the type II. The structures of the dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinediones were confirmed by elemental analysis and IR studies. The absence of any signal due to NH protons in NMR further supports the structure of the pyrimidinediones.

Experimental

The thioureas required for this work were prepared by condensing the aryl isothiocyanate with respective amines or condensing the arylamine with carbon disulphide in presence of potassium hydroxide¹³.

Synthesis of 1,3-diaryl dihydro-2-thioxo-4,6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinediones

A mixture of 1,3-diarylthiourea (0.04 mol), malonic acid (0.041 mol) and acetyl chloride (15 ml) was heated on a water bath under reflux for 30 minutes, the mixture first became a homogeneous fluid and later solidified to a compact light yellow

TABLE 1—1, 3-DIARYLDIHYDRO-2-THIOXO-4, 6 (1H, 5H)-PYRIMIDINEDIONES (Fig. 1)

Sl. No.	X	Y	M.P. °C	Yield %	Percentage				IR values	
					Found		Requires		ν >C=O cm ⁻¹	ν >C=S cm ⁻¹
					C	H	C	H		
1.	H	<i>p</i> -Methyl	215	51	65.6	4.4	65.8	4.5	1695,1710	1062
2.	H	<i>p</i> -Bromo	257	48	51.3	3.9	51.2	3.9	1700,1780	1064
3.	<i>p</i> -Bromo	<i>p</i> -Bromo	273	20	42.4	2.2	42.2	2.2	1693,1724	1064
4.	<i>p</i> -Bromo	<i>p</i> -Methyl	245	60	52.2	3.2	52.4	3.3	1695,1720	1062

TABLE 2—1, 3-DIARYL-5-(ARYLAZO) DIHYDRO-2-THIOXO-4, 6 (1H, 5H)-PYRIMIDINEDIONES (Fig. 2)

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Colour	Yield %	Molecular formula	Antibacterial Activity		
						<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>P. pyocyanea</i>
(X=H; Y= <i>p</i> -Methyl)								
1.	H	293	Y	73	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ S	(-)	(-)	(-)
2.	<i>o</i> -Methyl	285	Y	70	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₄ S	(-)	(+)	(-)
3.	<i>m</i> -Methyl	202	RO	68	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₄ S	(-)	(-)	(++)
4.	<i>p</i> -Methyl	289	O	71	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₄ S	(+)	(-)	(++)
5.	<i>o</i> -Methoxy	300	O	73	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₄ S	(+++)	(-)	(++)
6.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	300	Y	75	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₄ ClS	(+++)	(-)	(++)
7.	<i>m</i> -Chloro	259	YO	74	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₄ ClS	(+)	(-)	(++)
8.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	275	R	79	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₄ ClS	(+)	(-)	(++)
9.	<i>o</i> -Bromo	298	Y	78	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₄ BrS	(+)	(-)	(++)
10.	<i>p</i> -Bromo	265	SN	81	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₄ BrS	(-)	(-)	(++)
11.	<i>o</i> -Nitro	277	RB	80	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₆ S	(+)	(-)	(++)
12.	<i>m</i> -Nitro	247	B	84	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)	(++)
13.	<i>p</i> -Nitro	284	O	83	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₆ S	(+)	(+)	(++)
(X=H; Y= <i>p</i> -Bromo)								
14.	H	294-5	Y	75	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ BrS	(-)	(-)	(-)
15.	<i>o</i> -Methyl	287-8	YB	72	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₄ BrS	(-)	(-)	(-)
16.	<i>m</i> -Methyl	278	YB	70	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₄ BrS	(-)	(-)	(-)
17.	<i>p</i> -Methyl	272	B	73	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₄ BrS	(-)	(-)	(-)
18.	<i>o</i> -Methoxy	286-7	O	75	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₄ BrS	(+)	(-)	(-)
19.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	>300	O	77	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ ClBrS	(+)	(-)	(-)
20.	<i>m</i> -Chloro	263	Y	79	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ ClBrS	(-)	(-)	(-)
21.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	286-7	OSN	82	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ ClBrS	(-)	(-)	(-)
22.	<i>o</i> -Bromo	>300	O	82	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₂ S	(+)	(+)	(-)
23.	<i>p</i> -Bromo	286-7	O	83	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₂ S	(-)	(-)	(-)
24.	<i>o</i> -Nitro	281	B	85	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₆ BrS	(-)	(-)	(-)
25.	<i>m</i> -Nitro	253	R	84	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₆ BrS	(-)	(-)	(-)
26.	<i>p</i> -Nitro	294-5	RB	86	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₆ BrS	(-)	(-)	(-)
(X=Y= <i>p</i> -Bromo)								
27.	H	>300	OB	77	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₂ S	(+)	(-)	(+)
28.	<i>o</i> -Methyl	294-5	YB	73	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₂ S	(++)	(-)	(++)
29.	<i>m</i> -Methyl	281	O	73	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₂ S	(+++)	(-)	(+++)
30.	<i>p</i> -Methyl	>300	YO	75	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₂ S	(-)	(-)	(-)
31.	<i>o</i> -Methoxy	>300	RB	77	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₂ S	(-)	(-)	(-)
32.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	>300	YO	77	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ ClBr ₂ S	(-)	(-)	(-)
33.	<i>m</i> -Chloro	>300	YO	76	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ ClBr ₂ S	(+)	(-)	(-)
34.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	>300	B	82	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ ClBr ₂ S	(+)	(+)	(-)
35.	<i>o</i> -Bromo	>300	Y	81	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₃ S	(+)	(-)	(-)
36.	<i>p</i> -Bromo	>300	B	84	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₃ S	(++)	(-)	(-)
37.	<i>o</i> -Nitro	298-9	B	84	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₆ Br ₂ S	(++)	(-)	(-)
38.	<i>m</i> -Nitro	>300	O	86	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₆ Br ₂ S	(++)	(+)	(++)
39.	<i>p</i> -Nitro	297	OB	87	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₆ Br ₂ S	(++)	(++)	(++)
(X= <i>p</i> -Bromo; Y= <i>p</i> -Methyl)								
40.	H	291	O	74	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₄ BrS	(++)	(-)	(+++)
41.	<i>o</i> -Methyl	292	Y	71	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₄ BrS	(+++)	(-)	(+++)
42.	<i>m</i> -Methyl	292	RB	69	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₄ BrS	(++)	(+)	(+++)
43.	<i>p</i> -Methyl	>300	YO	72	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₄ BrS	(+++)	(+)	(+++)
44.	<i>o</i> -Methoxy	>300	YO	74	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₄ BrS	(+)	(-)	(+++)
45.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	>300	Y	76	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ ClBrS	(-)	(-)	(+++)
46.	<i>m</i> -Chloro	>300	YO	77	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ ClBrS	(+)	(-)	(+++)
47.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	>300	O	80	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ ClBrS	(++)	(-)	(+++)
48.	<i>o</i> -Bromo	298	YO	78	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₂ S	(+++)	(+++)	(+++)
49.	<i>p</i> -Bromo	288	O	82	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₂ S	(+++)	(+++)	(+++)
50.	<i>o</i> -Nitro	>300	RB	82	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₆ BrS	(-)	(-)	(-)
51.	<i>m</i> -Nitro	291	RB	84	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₆ BrS	(+)	(-)	(-)
52.	<i>p</i> -Nitro	227	SR	85	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₆ BrS	(+)	(-)	(-)

All the compounds gave satisfactory analysis for C and H.
B=Brown; N=Needles; O=Orange; S=Shining; R=Red; Y=Yellow.

crystalline mass. This was broken and finely powdered in a mortar in presence of water, the solid filtered, washed with hot ethanol and crystallised from glacial acetic acid or GAA-ethanol mixture. Four 1, 3-diaryl dihydro-2-thioxo-4, 6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinediones synthesised by this method are recorded in Table 1.

Synthesis of 1,3-diaryl-5-(arylozo) dihydro-2-thioxo-4, 6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinediones :

An ice-cold solution of 1, 3-diaryldihydro-2-thioxo-4, 6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinedione (0.002 mol) in dioxane (12 ml)-ethanol (25 ml) mixture, containing sodium acetate (5 g), was mechanically stirred and a diazotised solution of the base gradually added during stirring at 0-5°. The reaction mixture was further stirred for 5 minutes, diluted with ice-cold water and the coloured product so obtained was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol or glacial acetic acid or DMF or a mixture of any two of the above solvents. These compounds are entered in Table 2.

Antibacterial Properties :

All these synthesised compounds were tested for their antibacterial activity by the cup-plate agar diffusion method against three micro-organisms *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and *P. pyocyanea* at two different concentrations of 500 ug/ml and 250 ug/ml and the results with the latter are recorded in the Table 2.

The results of *in vitro* screening indicate that the compounds were more active against *S. aureus* and

P. pyocyanea and less active against *E. coli*. The azo derivatives obtained from 1-phenyl-3-(*p*-bromophenyl) dihydro-2-thioxo-4, 6 (1H, 5H)-pyrimidinedione did not exhibit activity against any of the three micro-organisms with a few exceptions and here again the order of activity was very low.

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